

Exploring the current state of research on neurodivergency in academic libraries

Catharina Ochsner

Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

The talk will report the results of a literature review on the topic of neurodivergency and academic libraries and provide an overview on the topic as well as the most important findings of the existing research. Although the topic has not been extensively covered by LIS research (Anderson, 2018, 2021; Belger & Chelin, 2013; Everhart & Anderson, 2020) or sufficiently considered in the academic library practice (Anderson & Robinson, 2024; Braumberger, 2021; Layden et al., 2021), neurodivergent users and staff are important stakeholders of the academic library (Robinson & Anderson, 2022), that researchers and practitioners need to be aware of in order to service and accommodate them (Belger & Chelin, 2013; Lawrence, 2013). Thus, the talk aims to educate and inform researchers, practitioners and students.

Value of the contribution

The talk will provide a theoretical foundation of knowledge on the topic and inform practitioners on guidelines and best practice examples for recommendable library services for neurodivergent academic library stakeholders, who consist of library users but also library staff and other faculty members (Harland et al., 2017). Additionally, the talk will uncover problematic social conventions about who LIS research considers to be important and support topics and individuals who are underrepresented in research and simultaneously not proficiently seen or heard in the library practice (Hinson-Williams, 2024).

Research outline

Neurodiversity is an umbrella term that describes a diversity of people with differently functioning brains, more specifically with differences in their neurocognitive functions. Compared to neurotypical people, whose brain functions fall under the societal standards of what is *healthy, normal* and *typical*, the neurocognitive functions of neurodivergent people differ or *diverge* from these standards (Walker, 2014). While more and more neurodivergent students enter the higher education environment (Clouder et al., 2020), academic libraries are not prepared to service neurodivergent users or accommodate neurodivergent staff (Anderson, 2018; Belger & Chelin, 2013; Everhart & Escobar, 2018). Within Library and Information Science (LIS), there is no introduction to, systematic overview or synthesis of the existing research on neurodivergency in academic libraries. Therefore, a scoping review of 44 scholarly publications on the topic was conducted. The review aimed to identify main topics within the literature, extract best practice examples, and uncover research gaps, that suggest a variety of possible directions for future research. The review was conducted in five steps: To begin with research questions (RQ's) were defined and then used as a foundation for the literature search. The final studies were then selected using criteria that was consistent with the RQ's and the aim of the review. Finally, the literature was charted for important contentual information, that was used to create a structure for the review (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005).

The review extracted three main topics of research: (1) Academic libraries and neurodivergency, which was concerned with neurodivergent staff and the state of neurodivergency education of academic library staff, (2) experiences of neurodivergent users and (3) recommendable services for neurodivergent library users. The literature described how library staff and LIS researchers are not educated enough on neurodivergency and the needs of neurodivergent stakeholders of the academic library (Anderson & Robinson, 2024; Dow et al., 2020; Giles-Smith & Popowich, 2020, 2023; Mulliken & Adkins, 2009), which negatively effects their services and therefore the experiences of neurodivergent library users and neurodivergent library staff. Furthermore, the review uncovered that existing research on the topics is often reproducing ableist stereotypes and using harmful and/or inaccurate language (Hinson-Williams, 2024). Future research needs close research gaps by studying and working with neurodivergent people but also by examining the social contexts around them and how systemic bias and social injustices are reflected and enacted within their institutions (Hinson-Williams, 2024; Magnusson, 2024). Researching neurodivergency at multiple intersections and developing services and strategies for neurodivergent stakeholders will furthermore also be beneficial for all library users and academic library staff (Anderson, 2018; Dow et al., 2020; Giles-Smith & Popowich, 2020; Hoover et al., 2013). Therefore, recommendable practices for libraries are to increase education about neurodivergency and the social context around disability and ableism (Hinson-Williams, 2024; Magnusson, 2024). Other good practice examples consisted of establishing closer communication and relationships between academic libraries and their neurodivergent stakeholders (Cho, 2018; Giles-Smith & Popowich, 2020; Jones, 2019, 2021, Pionke et al., 2019), offering diverse learning formats and materials (Cho, 2013; Chodock & Dolinger, 2009; Hoover et al., 2013; Jones, 2021), the reduction of stimuli and the provision of safe spaces that are designed with neurodivergent stakeholders in mind (Giles-Smith & Popowich, 2020; Nall, 2015; Pionke, 2017).

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